

D3.2 Report with processes and strategies for upscaling inventories of low-TRL Bio-based systems

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

ISO	International Organization for Standardization
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
PFD	Process Flow Diagram
TRL	Technology Readiness Level

PROJECT INFORMATION

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PARTNER N°	PARTICIPANT ORGANIZATION	ACRONYM
1 (Coord.)	CONTACTICA SL	CTA
2	AALBORG UNIVERSITET	AAU
3	LUXEMBOURG INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY	LIST
4	INSTITUT NATIONAL DES SCIENCES APPLIQUEES DE TOULOUSE	INSA
5	NORGES TEKNISK-NATURVITENSKAPELIGE UNIVERSITET	NTNU
6	BIOECONOMY FOR CHANGE	B4C
7	BUSINESS E-INCUBATOR GO-UP	GOUP
8	FUNDACION CENTRO DE SERVICIOS Y PROMOCION FORESTAL Y DE SU INDUSTRIA DE CASTILLA Y LEON	CESEFOR
9	SONAE ARAUCO PORTUGAL SA	SONAE
10	ASOCIACION PARA LA CERTIFICACION ESPANOLA FORESTAL	PEFC

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Abstract:	<p>This report presents a methodology to scale-up inventory data for emerging bio-based technologies that can be used for comparison with their fossil counterparts. The methodology is built upon chemical engineering principles, relying on a process flow diagram. This is implemented in specialized flowsheet software where simulation and optimization are performed in order to obtain more accurate inventories. The main advantage of this methodology is that it provides, at the same time, technical and environmental analysis which can be useful to guide decision-making towards more sustainable alternatives.</p>

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Guaranteeing a proper transition of a sustainable circular bioeconomy requires the selection of the emerging bio-based technology that can provide the most environmental benefits with good technical and economic performance. The assessment of these technologies must be performed from the early stages of design. Life cycle assessment (LCA) can contribute to predicting the environmental benefits of emerging technologies before their large-scale implementation.

Bio-based products are nowadays at low technology readiness levels (TRL) where most of the data is at laboratory scale. In order to perform a fair comparison of these technologies, the data of the emerging technology needs to be scaled up into a high TRL scenario. LCA calculation depends on the accuracy of the scale-up data.

Several methods have been proposed to scale-up inventory data based on many assumptions that provide many uncertainties to the LCA calculation. A more robust methodology based on chemical engineering is here proposed to be implemented in specialized flowsheet software to obtain more accurate inventories that include the optimization of the process. This methodology helps to position emerging bio-based technologies in a similar domain for comparison with their fossil counterparts. Furthermore, it provides technical and environmental analysis highlighting their potential benefits to guide decision-making towards a less-fossil and more sustainable bioeconomy.

INTRODUCTION

The Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is a holistic approach that allows for the calculation of the environmental impacts of a product or service providing a detailed analysis of all stages of their life cycle (cradle-to-grave) including natural resource extraction, manufacturing, transportation, use and maintenance, end-of-life and disposal. LCA is a standardized method conducted in accordance with the guidelines set by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO), series 14040 – 14046 (ISO, 2014), reason why its use has earned widespread trust from the scientific community, stakeholders, and industry professionals.

LCA can serve as a decision-making tool which can analyze the environmental performance of an industrial process at various levels, including individual on-site unit processes, background life cycle processes, specific time periods, or the entire life span of a plant. The integration of these considerations should be included since the early design phase of the product/service process in order to guide its development and to help choosing among different alternatives considering their environmental performance and to provide a basis for the projected and product improvement from an environmental point of view. This approach, named eco-design, includes LCA as a pillar, and was proposed for chemical processes (e.g. Azapagic et al., 2006; Mery et al., 2013), products (Luz et al., 2018), and later in the field of bio-based products and biotechnologies (e.g. Ahmadi et al., 2019).

The LCA standard methodology follows four key steps: 1) goal and scope definition, 2) Life Cycle Inventory (LCI), 3) Life Cycle Impact assessment (LCIA), and 4) result interpretation. The main part of the standard LCA methodology is the LCI which involves quantifying all inputs and outputs of the processes throughout a system's life cycle. This is considered as the most critical step in determining the relevance of the final results of an LCA. The inventory is categorized into foreground and background systems (Figure 1). The foreground system typically refers to the studied system which can be an innovative technology or process. It is the part of the system that the analyst models, which needs the development of new experiments and/or high-fidelity models. In contrast, the background system deals with the technological context including support processes, such as energy, transportation, and natural resource extraction, waste treatment. Usually, the background inventories are obtained from generic datasets, such as Ecoinvent, Agribalyse, ELCD, etc. During goal and scope definition, LCA practitioners need to think about available data sources to model foreground and background systems. Depending on the goal and scope definition foreground systems may include recycling and end-of-life of the product. For bio-based systems, however, end-of-life is often considered to be part of the background inventory since the main change from a fossil counterpart is the bio-based production of a targeted product.

Figure 1. General framework for LCA inventory for bio-based systems. Recycling and end-of-life could be part of both foreground and background inventories depending on goal and scope definition.

LCA is a comparative approach in which the environmental burdens of the system under study are regarded with respect to a baseline or reference system, normally existing technologies. The widely used databases for the reference systems contain data obtained or calculated at the current scale of implementation of a product/service. The use of LCA for emerging technologies depends on the quality of the data feeding the foreground inventory. In that context, the assessment of emerging technologies requires a scale-up of the energy and material flows at the scale at which the project will be once it is deployed in the real world. Only in this way the calculated environmental impacts of the emerging technology could be compared with a reference technology.

Technologies are identified according to their TRL where emerging technologies are considered as low TRL and fully commercial technologies as high TRL.

Available data from emerging technologies/products (low TRL) include lab experiments, patents, pilot implementation data, etc., which are mostly focused on isolated unit processes or technologies. From these data it is difficult to provide a holistic picture of the overall life cycle and to capture the resource usage, energy demands and/or waste generation.

Contrarily, at higher TRL the technology is usually better integrated with supply chains and other processes and is closer to being optimized for performance and efficiency. Furthermore, high TRL technologies are close to commercialization which can provide valuable insights for decision-making on market readiness, policy compliance, or investment.

Scaling-up of the foreground LCI is thus required to close data gaps and properly assess emerging technologies. As LCA must be performed at the same TRL as their current counterpart, optimization of the technology in a supply chain must be considered; otherwise, results might indicate that the emerging technologies perform worse than the current alternatives.

Several methods for scaling-up of foreground data of emerging technologies have been proposed including approximations (proxies), extrapolations, application of scaling factors and learning curves (van der Hulst et al., 2020), process engineering calculations (Piccinno et al., 2016), process based simulations (Ahmadi et al., 2019; Mery et al., 2013), scenarios. Review papers detailing the different methods can be found in (Erakca et al., 2024; Tsoy et al., 2020). A description of those methods is presented in the next subsection. Some efforts to harmonize the scale-up of the life cycle inventory have been reported (Arvidsson et al., 2024; Erakca et al., 2024; Piccinno et al., 2016; Tsoy et al., 2020) and extended to emerging bio-based systems (Cucurachi et al., 2022; de Souza et al., 2023). Authors agree that even if bio-based systems are promising options to replace fossil chemicals by the introduction, for instance, of biomass cascade frameworks (Liang et al., 2023; Rinke Dias de Souza et al., 2024), adequate robust scaling methods are required for the fair assessment and integration of any bio-based technology.

In this context, this report develops a methodology to scale-up foreground inventories based on process eco-design. The implementation is done upon chemical engineering software simulation and process-based calculation, that allows performing, *at the same time, technical and environmental assessments*. The approach stems from previous works in INSA-TBI, applied to drinking water plants (Mery et al., 2013), wastewater treatment plants, low molar mass dextran membranes (Prézéus et al., 2021), CO₂ carbon capture and utilization (Kanso et al., 2024, 2025) and desalination of seawater (Lorfing et al., 2022). However, a stepwise description has neither been published nor presented elsewhere. Therefore, the methodology is here explained in detail and extended to bio-based systems.

In the following subsections, the definition of TRL is presented and several methods for scaling-up inventories are reported and discussed. The next section develops the proposed methodology that is used within the LCA4BIO project to formulate scaled-up foreground inventories for emerging technologies. A discussion section highlighting the main advantages and limitations of the methodology closes this report.

Technology Readiness Level (TRL)

The necessity of scaling up processes from lab scale to industrial scale is a critical step to achieve the desired outcomes, such as increased production capacity, improved process efficiency, and enhanced economic viability. This progression is vital for transforming innovative laboratory findings into commercially viable and sustainable industrial processes. The concept of TRL was introduced into EU-funded projects in 2014 as part of the Horizon 2020 framework program to categorize the process development towards industrialization. The different levels are displayed in Figure 2 where the TRL scale describes 9 levels of technology maturity starting with the invention and ending at the commercialization of the technology/product.

Figure 2 – Scaling up process regarding the technology readiness levels (TRL). European Association of Research and Technology reading on the TRL scales (Adapted from EARTO 2014)

TRL 1 refers to a technology where scientific research has just begun and the basic principles of the idea are identified theoretically. At TRL 2, the basic principles are studied, and the initial experiments are conceived and tested to support the initial concept. However, the technology remains speculative. TRL 3 involves analytical and laboratory studies to determine if the technology is ready for development. Scientific feasibility is addressed by the realization of a proof-of-concept model. The implementation and validation of this model in a prototype within a lab environment position the technology at TRL 4. Once validated, tests in controlled but realistic environments are performed to prove technological feasibility, at this stage the technology reaches TRL 5. Up to this stage the concept validation is achieved, and several iterations occurred to formulate a feasible technology.

At TRL 6, the prototype is demonstrated in a real environment, confirming engineering feasibility. At TRL 7, the working model or prototype is demonstrated in an operational environment, typically under industrial conditions, confirming technological reliability. The technologies up to TRL 7 are considered as emerging technologies where the pilot production has been demonstrated and achieved. Although there could be a small production, the technology has not been introduced into an industrial plant where optimization of energy efficiency, materials use, and some performances can still improve the viability of the technology.

From TRL 8, the technology is considered mature as it is ready for integration into existing systems, including market introduction. Once proven operational, the technology reaches TRL 9 and is considered a commercial product. LCA is performed at these high TRLs.

In the frame of this project, emerging bio-based technologies will be considered as products derived from biomass that are not at commercial stage and placed at TRL below 8.

Scale-up methods for Foreground Life Cycle Inventory

The generation of inventories for low TRL technologies is highly uncertain since little or no information is available on how the technology will look at a more mature and larger scale. Compiling information of the LCI can be seen as a similar problem than for assessing technical feasibility of low TRL technologies. Therefore, designing high TRL technology based on low TRL data (e.g., lab experiments, patents, etc.) could benefit from the cooperation of chemical engineers and LCA practitioners (Simon et al., 2016). The (bio)chemical engineering employs the following elements : unit operations (the elementary step using a limited set of bio-physical phenomena), process (the ensemble of unit operations necessary to obtain the desired product), process flow diagram PFD (the combination of the unit operations linked by material and energy streams), energy integration (optimization of the energy flows in order to reduce the global energy demand), material integration (idem as energy, applied for a given material for instance water), utilities (secondary streams necessary to make the process functioning, e.g. vapor, process water, etc.).

Several methods have been proposed to scale-up low TRL data to build up foreground LCI (Erakca et al., 2024; Parvatker & Eckelman, 2019). Those methods are built upon the LCA thinking, starting by setting up the goal and scope of the studied low TRL, which comprises setting the targeted production (function unit) and proposing a flow diagram of the steps involved. In these works, scaling-up of foreground LCI implies scaling-up of the same processes that are involved in the production of low TRL product/service.

As many laboratory processes are not directly transferable to industrial scale, the first step for scaling-up is to adjust the lab scale diagram to project it into an industrial scale diagram, from which the processes can ultimately be upscaled. This is known as process flow diagram (PFD). The frameworks of (de Souza et al., 2023; Piccinno et al., 2016; Tsoy et al., 2020) proposed to start from the PFD and then to establish process yields, synergies, side streams at the desired scale. However, most of the approaches diverge on how to calculate the scaled-up flows concerning material and energy flows and emissions of the different processes.

Scaling-up methods for foreground data can be broadly distributed between three categories: 1) proxies, 2) extrapolated data, and 3) formal calculation. Multiple upscaling approaches for unit processes have been proposed to model industrial scale inventory data from lab or pilot scale data (Erakca et al., 2024; Parvatker & Eckelman, 2019). Table 1 reports the most used methods ranked according to the accuracy and uncertainty of estimates, where the more + signs means that the method is more accurate and less uncertain.

Table 1. The most used methods for scaling-up foreground LCI

Methods	Description	Accuracy
Process simulation tools	Use of flowsheet simulation software (e.g. Aspen Plus, ProSim, gPROMS, SuperProDesigner)	+++++
Process-based calculation	Calculations mass and energy balances calculated from physical laws equations, but without using simulation software	++++
Scenarios	Scenarios to evaluate a mix of technical parameters, efficiency gains, and technological improvements	++++
Stoichiometry	Elemental ratios of the products to scale the system and detailed process calculations include mass and energy balance equations	++
Scaling-up factors Empirical scaling	Use of learning curves and scaling-up factors	+++
Extrapolation	linear extrapolation or multiplication by scaling factors	++
Molecular structure methods	Physical and chemical properties to calculate the impact results	++
Proxy	Use of data from analogous, pre-existing technologies	+
No scaling-up	Studies that do not use low TRL data directly for foreground LCI	-

Although more uncertain, proxies are easy to consider using existing processes that are similar or by averaging results of multiple proxies. However, these are not recommended for low TRL technologies. Extrapolation-based upscaling approaches may be more effective for innovations that share the upstream and downstream infrastructure of the incumbent technology, where industrial scale data is available.

In cases where extrapolation-based upscaling methods are not effective due to data or time availability, (Simon et al., 2016) proposed to identify proxies-based function, dimension and similarity. However, many assumptions must be made to properly represent the processes. A similar process might be used instead to perform the same function such as a filter and a centrifuge, but their efficiency and energy requirements are different. Additional guides on what to consider when performing scaling-up have been addressed by van der Hulst et al. (2020) where the authors indicate considerations on process changes, size scaling and synergies at earlier TRLs based on high TRL technologies.

More accurate approaches encounter additional challenges. For instance, the use of flowsheet simulation software requires a high degree of knowledge on process design and software utilization. The advice and expertise of chemical engineers is needed to help LCA practitioners with the formal scaling-up of processes to include industrial synergies which can affect the overall performance of the production processes.

Scaling-up methodologies have also been developed according to applications. Chemical processes have been addressed in (Piccinno et al., 2016) where several process-based calculations are implemented to calculate energy requirements and a set of rules are given for the use of solvents, reactants and the calculation of yields.

With the increase interest on bio-based technologies, scale-up of foreground inventory have been addressed with the aim to perform prospective LCA, which implies that a technology is scaled-up (ex-ante LCA) and forecasted in time with changes into the future. The report of Cucurachi et al., (2022) provides a decision-making scheme to guide the choice of scaling-up methods prioritizing process simulations, if simulation software is available, in order to decreasing uncertainty on the estimation of the LCI. De Souza et al., (2023) proposed an ex-ante methodology on six parts: i) process description, ii) design of the PFD, iii) stating process synergies (i.e., material and energy recovery) from the PFD, iv) improvement of yields (considering stoichiometric yields or close to theoretical yields), v) side streams (adjusted stoichiometrically), and vi) scaling-up each process separately. These approaches consider that even if bio-based and conventional chemical processes are different in their production routes, the functionality of a given unit operation is often the same irrespective of the product produced, making existing upscaling knowledge of the chemical industry relevant to the bio-chemical industry.

PROPOSED METHODOLOGY FOR FOREGROUND LCI

The goal of a scale-up foreground LCI is to provide accurate information to conduct LCA whose results can be employed with high confidence on decision-making strategies for the support and development of more environmentally friendly technologies.

In order to provide less uncertain LCI, the proposed methodology is based on chemical engineering using specialized software simulation and process-based calculation (completing the simulation). On this basis, the obtained results are two-folded providing inventories to perform, at the same time, technical and environmental assessments. This methodology is based on the eco-design approach presenting a process modeling – LCA framework, developed in Ahmadi et al., (2019); Bisinella de Faria et al., (2015); Mery et al., (2013) with specificity according to the case study).

The main objective of the developed scale-up framework is to gather logically and systematically organized data from an LCA perspective, enabling the simulation of the process at a larger scale.

The methodology is described as a guideline comprising six steps which are displayed in Table 2. The detailed description of each step is developed in the following subsections.

Table 2. Guideline to build a scale-up foreground inventory for emerging technologies

Step	Description
1 Definition of the studied technology	Identify the emerging technology/product and prepare preliminary data from literature, patents, technical results
2 Goals	Set the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) of the desired production: scale, purity of the product
3 Construction of a PFD	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identify the main steps involved in the production process 2. Define up-streaming and down-streaming unit operations 3. Perform unit operations design with hypothesis according to tables of D3.3.
4 Integration and optimization of the complete Process Flow Diagram	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Complete the PFD with the required fluid transports 2. Simulate the complete process from raw materials to high purity products at the targeted scale respecting the already set KPI 3. Make a Pinch analysis for heat integration 4. Integrations of different streams to gain material (e.g. water) and energy
5 Build the foreground inventory	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Get information from the process simulation software (mass and energy balances) to feed the scaled-up foreground inventory 2. Identify the background datasets for raw materials, utilities, waste treatments 3. Allocate co-products
6 Foreground inventory analysis	Complete scaled-up foreground inventory and perform sensitivity analysis

1. Definition of the studied technology

The first step consists of the selection of a target product and the emerging technology to produce it. This task involves performing a literature review to explore the applications of the product as well as the current technology to produce in order to set a benchmark of comparison (counterpart). This benchmark will set up a target to establish the improvements and advantages of using emerging technologies (e.g., better yield, use of other substrates, less co-products, bio-based route). Data about the emerging technology (low TRL) should be identified from lab/pilot experiments, patents or scientific articles to set up the necessary materials to produce the targeted product as well as to assess the conversion performance including the production of co-products and waste. The process flow diagram of the benchmark technology and the emerging technology (if available) could be of great use to compare both routes. However, PFD for emerging technologies are not often available and the next steps will guide towards its design and utilization to get the LCI.

2. Goals

In order to make a fair comparison of the emerging technology with its counterpart production, it must be set to an equal objective set by Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). *To set the objective, start with the end in mind.* This means targeting the scale of your system by setting as objective a desired production amount of product per year, where the final product needs to comply with certain purity and conditions (e.g., pressure, temperature, pH, physical state, etc.). These KPIs set the targeted scale of the emerging technology to calculate the substrates needed for its production. As most low TRL data is obtained from experiments of short duration, the production must be scaled up to a yearly production.

For a continuous production, the productive time should be estimated, e.g. 8000 hours/year. In case of discontinuous (e.g. seasonal, intermittent, etc.) production, an approximate scheduling must be envisioned in order to evaluate the necessary production capacity (e.g. volumes) and the effective material and energy flows.

3. Construction of a Process Flow Diagram

With the objectives and the emerging technology in mind, the goal is to sketch up and qualitatively describe a potential industrial process chain, based on similar but well-known processes. Once defined, quantitative data could be obtained. The construction of a PFD requires expertise of chemical engineers to set up the proper technology for each part. A PFD is regularly composed of upstreaming and down-streaming processes with respect to the main unit process which represent the innovation. The firsts refer to the pretreatment and conditioning of raw materials, while the lasts deal with separation and purification processes to obtain the targeted product at the desired conditions. Thus, in this methodology, the PFD is divided into three parts: 1) upstreaming processes 2) the main process (emerging technology), and 3) down streaming processes. This partition allows that the emerging technology can be also placed in the upstreaming or down-streaming processes. Each process in the PFD is here denoted as a unit operation. A general framework for the construction of PFD is displayed in Figure 3 where the first part to model corresponds to the main process, followed by the up-streaming and finally the down-steaming processes.

Figure 3. Proposed methodology for the construction of PFD.

The use of biomass for the production of bio-based products follows several stages that are generalized in Figure 4 where three types of bio-based products can be obtained. Biomass encounters the first mechanical pretreatment aiming for size reduction for further processes. Once reduced, biomass can follow two pathways depending on the type of biomass. Wood-based biomass can be considered as a product (1) for which conditioning operations, such as glue applying, pressing and drying could be applied to create wood-based materials (e.g. wood panels). Non-wood-based biomasses follow chemical, physicochemical or biological pretreatments to obtain more easily degradable products. After pretreatment, separation is required to recover solvents, and to purify the obtained products (2). If lignocellulosic biomass is taken as an example, the bio-based products (2) could be lignin, cellulose, hemicellulose. These three outputs can be considered as products or be converted into other chemicals.

The most common biorefinery routes use cellulose and hemicellulose to obtain highly degradable sugars (e.g., glucose, xylose, furans). Therefore, these can go through a conversion stage that can include hydrolysis and/or fermentation to be transformed into different high value-added products. Further separation and purification of the outputs of the fermentation is needed to obtain the target product (3). Finally, product conditioning operations are used to get bio-based product (3) the at the desired KPIs.

Figure 4. General flowsheet diagram of Bio-based Systems (BbS) including the most used unit operations for the production chain.

Main process of the low-TRL

The main process is the emerging technology to be assessed. For instance, if the main process (unit operation) corresponds to the reaction step where target product is formed material inputs are reactants (biomass, substrates), solvents, and possibly catalysts (substances, microorganisms) whereas the energy input is mainly required for heating and stirring of the reaction mixture. The outputs of this process are a mixture containing the target product and, eventually, co-products, and non-reacted inputs.

The inputs and outputs must be identified first based on low TRL data as well as energy balances (if available). These data will serve to identify the governing mechanisms of this 'main' process regarding the physical, chemical or biological phenomena. The most important part is to identify the rate-determining step to set how this will be influenced by a change in scale. The kinetics will inform about the influence of temperature, stability, yields and allows to determine all other properties depending on the mixture composition (e.g. physical state, viscosity, density, etc). Once identified, this information could be used to develop a mathematical model to represent the productivity and resolve it with the corresponding thermodynamic and kinetic parameters. The model could be used also to evaluate the process performance depending on the most important operation conditions. This will allow us to perform a fair scale-up of the main process. Simulations of the main process are performed at the targeted scale within specialized flowsheet software, or with a home-made dedicated software. The most important parameters to be considered in function of unit operation are described in D3.3. Once the main process has been simulated, the processes to pre-treat its inputs and to separate its outputs must be defined.

Up-streaming process

Several processes can be used to obtain the required inputs (substrates) of the main process. Literature review is performed to select a well-known technology (high-TRL) to obtain the substrates. If there is not a high-TRL pathway the one having the best yield or the best-known technology must be chosen. Similar to the main process, data about up-streaming unit operations need to be collected in order to model those processes. The choice of unit operations can be done according to their function. Tables representing each unit operation and their main parameters are presented in LCA4Bio D3.3: Dataset with upscaling factors and functions.

The ensemble of unit operations for up-streaming should be modelled in the flowsheet software and coupled to the model of the main process to build-up the first part of the PFD.

Down-streaming process

The outputs of the main process must be separated to get the targeted product with the desired KPIs. Several unit operations for down-streaming processes already exist for chemical processes. However, the development of a flowsheet for the recovery and purification of a biological product is a creative process drawing from experience and imagination of engineers. A literature-based analysis must be undertaken to select the best separation alternatives (e.g., less energy consumption) and to identify different processes used for similar mixtures. Some heuristics can help to design the train of separation operations of the down-streaming process (Harrison et al., 2015): 1) first remove the easiest-to-remove impurities; 2) select processes that make use of the greatest differences in the properties of the product and its impurities; 3) select and sequence processes that exploit different separation driving forces; 4) the most difficult and expensive separations are to be performed last.

The separation train configuration depends on the efficiency of each unit operation and its outputs, which determine the subsequent unit operations to be linked in series. The co-products are also separated and purified depending on their later use. The down-streaming processes are the most energy consuming processes, but they provide recirculation of solvents and catalysts, as well as the product and co-products to be further valorized. The Tables reported in the deliverable D3.3 present the main parameters needed for their modeling,

the calculations to add to software processes and the level of accuracy that can be attained. It is worth noting that if large amounts of co-products are produced, several unit operations for their separation and purification will be necessary. These co-products can be valorized in separate routes.

4. Integration and optimization of the Process Flow Diagram

At this point, the complete PFD has been modelled. The models provide essentially accurate mass and energy balances per unit operation, as well as efficiency calculations with the required degree of accuracy. All unit operations can be simulated together from the raw materials up to the target product. The PFD needs to be completed with the required utilities for fluid transport and energy transfer (i.e., heat exchangers). Simulations are performed at the desired scale respecting the KPIs, especially the production target of a certain amount of product per year.

Additional optimization of the PFD can be performed, such as heat integration. For this task, pinch analysis can be used to recover the heat of different streams and diminished energy consumption. Benchmarking or comparative analysis with alternative PFDs could be implemented. If similar processes exist, a validation could be made by verifying that the mass and energy balances fall within the given ranges.

5. Build the foreground inventory

The calculated mass and energy balances of the PFD are collected from the simulation software to fill up the material and energy inventory that feed the Life Cycle Inventory. Elementary flows representing emissions are obtained mainly in the steps involving combustion since gases might be emitted. However, air emissions can occur from by-products of chemical reactions, fermentation gas, volatile (organic) solvents, and decomposition of unreacted parts. Furthermore, water emissions are mainly considered from all the liquid outputs that are not considered as products, via their treatments. In most cases, as only traces of co-products are left, the output could be taken as wastewater.

The purity and properties (KPIs) of the obtained products could vary from a technology to another and from a utilization to another. Moreover, the biomass used as raw material to produce the target product can influence the proportion and type of co-products. In general, the biomasses are not interchangeable without consequences on the outputs. Moreover, changes in the process configuration are sometimes needed.

The obtained foreground inventory is linked to the background processes. This needs the integration of the foreground system in the complete life cycle by adopting an allocation modeling scheme (attributional, consequential, etc.). Nevertheless, allocation of co-products is not straightforward. The preferred method of allocation is system expansion (ISO-14044, 2006) by finding equivalent existent materials to be replaced. However, if no equivalent materials are found redefining the functional unit or system boundaries to include all functions is necessary (Cucurachi et al., 2022), or a different type of allocation could be considered: mass, energy, exergy or economic value becomes necessary (ISO-14044, 2006). Economic allocation is often preferred because it doesn't need complex handling of the linked processes. The multi-products issue in LCA is investigated in WP3 and WP4.

6. Foreground inventory analysis

After allocation, the foreground LCI is complete. Further analysis, such as sensitivity analysis, could be performed to verify the effect of changes on parameters, yields, energy efficiencies. For bio-based products, an important factor to evaluate is the biomass variability as its composition can change depending on the source. Exploration about the factor of uncertainties in the foreground LCI is here associated to each unit operation of the PFD. These factors of uncertainty can be calculated from a statistic comparison of simulation versus real data of well-known unit operations.

ADVANTAGES AND LIMITATIONS OF THE PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The main challenges of generating scaled-up inventory data for emerging technologies are data availability and the uncertainty linked to each assumption of the scale-up.

The proposed methodology follows a chemical engineering-based approach in which simulation software is employed to calculate the material and energy flows that will be fed to the inventory. The core of this method is the construction of a process flow diagram comprising the modeling of each unit operation of the transformation of raw materials into a target product. The use of model-based simulations can bring the advantage to reduce the level of uncertainty when scaling-up, since most of the unit operations are well-known in chemical engineering and their modeling principles have been well-studied. However, uncertainty remains in the emerging technology for which only laboratory data exists, and it can grow as data quality decreases.

The main advantage of the proposed methodology is that it can provide technical and environmental analysis at the same time. This can be of great value for decision-making on their eco-design and can help to identify environmental hotspots and technical bottlenecks before its implementation. Nevertheless, the main disadvantage is that its use is not straightforward since modeling of unit operations requires chemical engineering knowledge. Another issue is how to obtain an uncertainty factor to guarantee that the approach is valid. The uncertainty factors could be aggregated to indicate the main cause of uncertainty.

Our methodology can be applied either for chemical or for bio-based processes. However, allocation of bio-based processes needs to be carefully performed since those products might not have the properties than their counterparts. Additionally, they can provide new functionalities and/or services that have not been evaluated and need to be modelled up to a well-defined counterpart product and/or allocated economically. Another recommendation to handle multifunctionality of products is to provide a comprehensive description of reference system and to consider cradle-to grave boundaries, including end-of life impacts.

A general challenge is the availability of high-quality data since laboratory or patent data is often not properly explained which hinders their accurate scale-up and thus the robustness of the LCA assessment and the results comparability with other technologies.

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